

MORI-TANAKA METHODS FOR MICROMECHANICS OF RANDOM FIBRE COMPOSITES

Stepan V. Lomov^{1,2}, Yasmine Abdin^{1,2}, Atul Jain^{1,3}

¹Department of Materials Engineering, KULeuven
Kasteelpark Arenberg 44, B-3001 Leuven, Belgium,

²SIM Program Nanoforce, Technologiepark Zwijnaarde 935, Zwijnaarde, Belgium, B-9052.

³Siemens Industry Software NV, Leuven

Email: Stepan.Lomov@mtm.kuleuven.be

Keywords: Short fibre composites, modelling, fatigue, damage, Mori-Tanaka

ABSTRACT

The paper investigates the application of Eshelby solution and Mori-Tanaka homogenisation/strain concentrators algorithm for random short fibre composites micromechanics: stiffness homogenisation, calculation of stresses in fibres and on the fibre/matrix interface with subsequent debonding modelling. It is shown that Mori-Tanaka algorithm, applied to an assembly of randomly oriented, variable length inclusions provides adequate predictions for the homogenised stiffness, for stresses in the inclusions and on the interface and for progressive debonding of the fibres.

1. INTRODUCTION

The problem of calculating the effective response is of fundamental importance for multi-scale analysis of fibre reinforced composite materials. This typically involves calculating the average stress fields in a representative volume element (RVE) and also relies on microstress details to model damage and non-linearity at the constituent level (micro-scale analysis). Method of inclusions based methods provide a viable method to calculate the effective response of composite materials. These methods are based on the solution of Eshelby [1] which describes the stress state in an ellipsoidal elastic inclusion trapped in an infinite sea of elastic matrix. Starting from this solution and assuming different interactions between inclusions several formulations have been developed by which the effective response of an inclusion assembly can be calculated; collectively these methods are sometimes named mean field homogenization schemes. Benveniste [2] proposed a method to use the Mori-Tanaka formulation [3] to calculate the effective response of composite materials. Once an inclusion assembly is defined, these methods are quite easy to implement. They are computationally cheap and give access to rich information about stresses in the constituent level.

However, there is a lot of literature pointing out to theoretical shortcomings of these methods. Li [4] placed stringent conditions on the applicability of these methods for composite materials. According to him, an inclusion based method can be used only if it returns a diagonally symmetric effective stiffness matrix, internal consistency relations between the effective modulus are satisfied and that the solution must satisfactorily deal with both dilute reinforcement condition and close to 100% inclusion volume fraction. Also, the values of effective properties must lie between the upper and lower bounds formulated by Hashin and Shtrikman [5]. Benveniste [6] demonstrated that both the Mori-Tanaka formulation and the self-consistent schemes yield a symmetric stiffness tensor only if all the inclusions have the same aspect ratio and orientation. Ferari [7] described that these methods fail to work when

there are high concentration of inclusions. As a result very stringent conditions are often placed in the applicability of these methods, Pierard et al. [8] proclaim that these methods work only if all the inclusions have the same aspect ratio and are all aligned in the same direction.

Despite the presence of such stringent requirements, there is a substantial amount of literature which rely upon simplifying assumptions to ensure a tractable analysis of complex inclusion assemblies, representing complex reinforcement geometry, and these methods give fairly reasonable predictions. These methods are being extensively used to calculate the effective response of a wide range of fibre reinforced composite materials not restricted to the case where the shape of inclusions are directly approximate to the ellipsoidal shape but also to a range of composites where the geometry of fibre is complex for example curved fibre composites, textile composites and coated inclusions. In all such cases the fibrous material of the reinforcement is replaced for the analysis by an assembly of ellipsoidal inclusions. Also, though these inclusion based methods were initially aimed at modelling the linear material response, a wide range of non-linear material models like plasticity, viscoplasticity, Neo-Hookean etc and damage modelling like fibre matrix debonding, fibre breakage have also been implemented. The present paper summarises the use of Mori-Tanaka methods for modelling of elastic, non-linear and damage behaviour of short fibre composites.

2. MORI-TANAKA AND PSEUDO-GRAINS [9]

We compare the predictions of stresses in individual inclusions by the Mori-Tanaka formulation and the pseudo-grain Mori-Tanaka (PGMT) [8]. To compare the inclusion average stresses predictions by the Mori-Tanaka formulation and PGMT a series of RVE were created. The volume fraction of the inclusions varied from 1% to 25%. For all the calculations, a second order orientation tensor “ \mathbf{a} ”, was fed as an input to describe the orientation distribution of the inclusions. Complete information about the orientations of inclusions is based on a fourth order orientation tensor. If the orientation is fixed or uniformly random the closure from second order orientation tensor \mathbf{a} to the fourth order orientation tensor is exact. However for orientations which are neither uniformly random nor fixed, the estimation of the fourth order orientation tensor from the second order orientation tensor is not exact and some approximation is needed. In such cases, orthotropic closure method as described by Cintra and Tucker [10] was used for both the Mori-Tanaka and PGMT formulation.

The calculations performed can be grouped into three categories (Figure 1). A *first set of models* studied had inclusions with aspect ratio 3 and volume fraction 0.161 (equivalent to mass fraction of 30%, which is a typical value for injection moulded composites) were fully aligned to each other. For this case, two RVE are considered the first one had all the inclusions aligned in the same direction with value of orientation angle $\varphi=0$, whereas the second model has all inclusions with value of orientation angle $\varphi=90$. This set of calculations was performed to compare the predictions of the Mori-Tanaka formulation with the FE results. PGMT for such configurations is equivalent to Mori-Tanaka formulation, since such an RVE which is already a biphase composite, pseudo-grain discretization leads to creation of a single pseudo-grain. A *second set of models* was built with approximate 2D-planar uniformly random orientations. The different volume fractions considered were 0.01, 0.1 and 0.25%. A *third set of calculations* were aimed at comparing the predictions of the Mori-Tanaka and the PGMT formulation when the assumptions of mean strain and image strain were said to be too simplistic. First a model with non-uniform 2D-planar orientation is considered. Inclusions had an aspect ratio of 3, while the orientation distribution for this case was taken to be $a_{11}=0.65$, $a_{22}=0.35$. Finally a comparison was made for the case of mixed aspect and mixed orientations, the model consisted of inclusions having aspect ratio 3 and 15. The inclusions with aspect ratio 15 were modelled as a spherocylinder while the inclusions with aspect ratio 3 were modelled as ellipsoids. The orientation of the inclusion with lower aspect ratio is an approximation of 2D-planar uniform random, while longer inclusions are aligned in one direction. This particular configuration was chosen to create a RVE so as to test the validity of the assumptions of the Mori-Tanaka formulation even in cases when there are inclusions with different aspect ratios as well as completely different orientation tensor for inclusion of each aspect ratio.

Figure 1: Three variants of the inclusions configurations: (a) parallel inclusions; (b) 2D planar uniformly random orientation; (c) mixed shapes and orientations

Figure 2

Figure 3

Figure 2: Inclusion average and phase average stresses for an RVE with fully aligned inclusions, with aspect ratio 3 and $\nu_f = 0.164$ for an applied strain of 1%, (a) S11 for inclusions with $\phi = 0$, (b) $\phi = 90$, (c) S22 for inclusions with $\phi = 0$, (d) $\phi = 90$

Figure 3: Inclusion average stresses in the global loading direction, for random orientation of inclusions, applied strain 1%, (a, d), $\nu_f = 0.1$, with orientation tensor ($a_{11}=0.51, a_{22}=0.49$); (b, e) $\nu_f = 0.01$, with orientation tensor ($a_{11}=0.54, a_{22}=0.46$) (c, f) $\nu_f = 0.25$, with orientation tensor ($a_{11}=0.52, a_{22}=0.48$), (a-c) S11, (e-f) S22

Figure 4: The scatter of average stresses in inclusions with respect to orientation for inclusions with aspect ratio 3. RVE consisted of randomly oriented inclusions with aspect ratio 3 and aligned inclusions with aspect ratio 15. (a) S11 (b) S22. (c) Polynomial curve fit of mean of inclusion average stresses of FE, also displaying confidence interval of $\alpha=0.05$ of stresses for S11 (d) S22

The results are shown in Figures 2-4. The Mori-Tanaka formulation predicted correctly the inclusion average stresses whereas the pseudo-grain discretization led to incorrect prediction of the inclusion average stresses. After pseudo-grain discretization the individual inclusions are discretized in a field of inclusions having same orientation and aspect ratio to itself is therefore influenced by only inclusions which have orientation and aspect ratio. PGMAT formulation separates inclusions at a scale which it should not, this leads to loss of some interactions between the inclusions and also introduces spurious

interactions between inclusions having the same orientation and aspect ratio. Both the Mori-Tanaka and PGMT formulations predicted similar values of the phase average stress. For the case of the Mori-Tanaka formulation the stresses (and strains) in the individual inclusions are averaged to estimate the strain concentration factor which is then used to calculate the effective stiffness. However, in PGMT, the effective stiffness of the individual grains is first estimated by the Mori-Tanaka formulation and then the effective stiffness of the composite is calculated as a volume weighted average of the stiffness of the individual grains. In a composite material having isotropic inclusions and matrix showing linear behaviour, the pseudo-grain discretization is equivalent to redistributing the image strain unevenly among the inclusions. In such cases the predictions of phase average stresses of PGMT should be in good agreement with the predictions of Mori-Tanaka. This is also what was observed in our calculations.

Comparisons for stress predictions by the Mori-Tanaka formulation and PGMT for individual inclusions were performed for a wide range of inclusion configurations, each having almost a 2D-orientation of inclusions. In all the cases the Mori-Tanaka formulation proved to give good correlation with the finite element calculations. Pseudo-grain discretization however failed to give good estimates of the stress level in the individual inclusions while predicting correctly the phase average stresses. The assumption of the mean strain in the Mori-Tanaka formulation seems to be a reasonable estimate, even in cases when there was statistical distribution of orientation and length in inclusions. For the matrix phase, no significant differences were reported in the prediction of stress levels by full Mori-Tanaka formulation and by Mori-Tanaka formulation after pseudo-grain discretization.

The scatter of deviation of the FE results for individual inclusions from the average trends predicted by the Mori-Tanaka formulation increases with increase in volume fraction of inclusion and also quite significantly when there is a length distribution. In such cases, the Mori-Tanaka formulation can only predict the general trend of stresses in inclusions with respect to orientations. It can be concluded that Mori-Tanaka formulation is a better approximation of reality and should be used as the standard (“first choice”) mean field homogenization method, particularly if the stresses in individual inclusions are important for further analysis.

3. MORI-TANAKA FOR NON-STRAIGHT FIBRES

Random fibre composites can contain wavy fibres, as well as straight ones. For short glass fibres with length in the range 0.5 ... 5 mm, corresponding to elongation in the range 25...250) the latter case is typical. If the fibres elongation is higher, the fibres in the composite can easily be wavy. Examples are polymers reinforced with carbon nanotubes (typical elongation over 1000) and composites reinforced by discontinuous steel fibres. Huysmans et al. [11] has proposed a method of taking into account the fibre waviness when constructing the set of inclusions for application of the Mori-Tanaka homogenisation. They proposed taking into account the reduction of load carrying capability of curved segments by the so-called Poly-Inclusion (P-I) model. In the P-I model a curved fibre is divided into a sufficiently large number of smaller segments, the effect of segment curvature is taken into account by assuming a simple inversely-proportional relationship between the equivalent inclusion's length and the original segment's curvature as follows:

$$a_r = \beta * \frac{R}{d} \quad (1)$$

where a_r is the aspect ratio of the equivalent inclusion, β is the efficiency (proportionality) factor, R is the radius of curvature of original segment and d is the segment diameter. Segments with higher local curvatures are modelled with equivalent inclusions with lower aspect ratios, reflecting lower efficiency of curved segment.

In the present paper, the P-I model is applied to discontinuous wavy fibres, with the main application to short steel fibres reinforcing thermoplastic polypropylene matrix. The predictive abilities of the P-I

model for average stresses in equivalent inclusions are compared with full-scale FE results of the average stresses in the original wavy fibre segments.

In the first test case (Figure 5a), a volume element (VE) containing a single half circular fibre is considered. The fibre has a constant curvature k of 0.1. In the second test case (Figure 5b) VE contains wavy steel fibres extracted from micro-CT scans of steel fibre reinforced composites. Details of the micro-CT scans and of the geometry of the VE can be found in [12]. The considered VE includes 30 fibres which has been previously reported as the sufficient number of inclusions to form a representative VE of random fibres. The diameter of all fibres was set to $d = 8 \mu\text{m}$ which is the nominal diameter given in the fibres datasheet. The fibre volume fraction of the VE containing 30 fibres is the same as of the scanned composite sample. For all cases, a homogeneous uniaxial strain $\bar{\epsilon}$ of 1% is applied in transverse (Y-Y, see the coordinate notation in Figure 5) direction. Transverse loading is considered due to its significant influence on interface failure and consequently fibre-matrix debonding, the major damage mechanism in short fibre composites.

Figure 5: Test cases for models of wavy fibres composites: (a) circular arc fibre and its inclusions representation (five segments); (b) random fibres from micro CT image

Figure 6 shows the results of modelling of the first test case. The value of $\beta = \frac{\pi}{2}$ best correlated with the overall elastic properties and the local stresses in inclusions for this test case. The predictions of the P-I model converge with increase of the number of segments starting from the value of $N_{segments} = 5$. The trends of analytical P-I model correspond to the trends of FE simulations of equivalent inclusions. The discrepancies between predictions of analytical P-I model and real stress fields in wavy fibre is due to loss of connectivity of equivalent segments.

Figure 7 shows the predictions of the P-I model compared to FEA for the second test case. Variations of the β factor are shown. It should be noted that for the whole VE, the same β value was used for all fibres and segments, either $\beta = \pi/2$ or $\beta = \pi$. For all fibres, 20 segments were used. For clarity, an example of two fibres with exact matching of segments between P-I and FEA is shown. Figure 7 shows that the P-I model gives very good agreement with FEA for segments axial stresses. In this case, generally, an efficiency factor of $\beta = \pi$ gives the best matching with experimental data.

Figure 6. Comparison of P-I model predictions of average local stresses σ_{33} in equivalent inclusions of the first test case (half circular fibre): (a) with variations of number of segments; (b) different volume fractions

Figure 7: Comparison of P-I model predictions of average local stresses in equivalent inclusions of the third test case (VE of real fibres) with variations of the efficiency factor β against full FEA against full FEA. The figure shows the comparison for an example of two selected fibres from the VE for (a) for axial segment stresses σ_{33} , (b) for transverse segment stresses σ_{22} of the first fibre and (c), (d) for the second fibre. k is the curvature

To summarize, it has been shown that the P-I model generally gives good agreement of the homogenized global elastic response of VEs of wavy fibres as well as local stress fields in inclusions.

Predictions of axial stress states in equivalent inclusions depicted very good agreement with FE results. Trends of normal stress states in equivalent inclusions showed less agreement with FE results in cases of fibres with variable local curvatures. Nevertheless, overall predicted values were still within reasonable accuracy.

4. MORI-TANAKA FOR PROGRESSIVE DEBONDING [13]

There are several methods to calculate the onset of debonding within the framework of mean field homogenization. A modified Coulomb criterion which combines the effect of the normal and the shear stress at the interface by means of an empirical parameter used for the analysis presented in this paper. Once the onset of debonding is correctly predicted, the next challenge is to treat the fibres with debonded interface. Debonded interface cannot be treated directly within the framework of mean field homogenization since the mean field homogenization formulations are based on the assumption of perfect adhesion between the fibre and the matrix. Zhao and Weng [14, 15] and Fitoussi et al. [16] proposed a scheme to estimate effective properties of a composite containing perfectly bonded inclusions as well as inclusions with debonded interface by replacing an inclusions with debonded interface by a perfectly bonded “equivalent inclusion” with changed stiffness, so that Eshelby solution and consequently mean field homogenization schemes could be used. The method of Zhao and Weng is primarily focused on isotropic spherical inclusions, while Fitoussi et al. apply the approach to sheet molding compound (SMC) composites and they claimed that for those composites the debonded interface was primarily in the equator of the inclusions which are almost perpendicular to the tensile loading direction. In injection molded composites, the aspect ratio of inclusion is much smaller than in SMC (but the inclusions are not spheroidal either) and consequently the stress build up in the fibre is not enough for inducing fibre breakage without initiation of fibre matrix debonding first, thus debonded interface at the tip of fibre must be accounted for. This paper proposes to treat debonded inclusions by the introduction of an “Equivalent Bonded Inclusion” (*EqBI*). The properties of the *EqBI* are calculated as function of the reduced stress transfer in the interface due to debonded interface. This new approach is able to take into account exact region and extent of debonded interface.

There exist two methods to model the matrix non-linearity, namely the secant modulus and the tangent modulus approaches. In this paper the secant approach as proposed by Tandon and Weng [17] is used. The behavior of the matrix phase is described by a secant operator which links the average stress in the matrix to the average strain.

It is proposed in this paper to replace a fibre with debonded interface by an equivalent bonded inclusion (*EqBI*). The stiffness of the *EqBI* are calculated in such a way that the *EqBI* is mechanically equivalent to the debonded inclusion. To estimate the stiffness tensor of an *EqBI*, a VE consisting of a single inclusion is assumed and approximate expressions for the stress (re)distribution in the inclusion due to debonded interface are derived. The average stresses in the inclusions are then calculated. The diagonal terms, C'_{ii} of the stiffness tensor of the *EqBI* are determined as a product of the corresponding diagonal terms (C_{ii}) of the stiffness tensor of the original inclusion and the ratio of the average stress in the inclusion with debonded interface to the average stress that would be built in the inclusion, if it was perfectly bonded:

$$C'_{ii} = \frac{\langle \sigma'_{ii} \rangle}{\langle \sigma_{ii} \rangle} C_{ii} \quad (2)$$

where C'_{ii} , C_{ii} are the stiffness component of the *EqBI* and the original inclusion which relates the average stress σ_{ii} in a composite to applied strain ϵ_{ii} , σ'_{ii} and σ_{ii} are stresses in the inclusion with debonded and perfect interface respectively; $\langle \rangle$ indicates volume averaging. The non-diagonal terms of the stiffness tensor are calculated assuming that the Poisson's ratio of the inclusion does not change. By this method it can be ensured that the effective stress response of the two systems viz. RVE with *EqBI* and the original RVE with fibre having debonded interface is the same. Depending upon the direction of applied load with respect to the fibre axis, debonded interface surfaces could lie (A) at the

tip or (B) elsewhere on the surface of the inclusion; these two configurations are named Type A and Type B respectively (Figure 8). The summary of the formulae is given in Table 1.

Figure 8: Schematic representation of the concept of the equivalent bonded inclusion (EqBI) used to calculate the effective properties of SFRC containing inclusions with debonded interface. Two different configurations of the debonded interface (type A and B) are shown as EqBI of different colour.

Table 1: A summary of the expressions of the stresses in inclusions with debonded interface, σ'_{incl} .

Stiffness component	Type A	Type B
C_{33}	$\sigma'_{incl} = E_f \cdot \epsilon_1 - (E_f \cdot \epsilon_1 - 2 \cdot \tau_t \cdot s \cdot m) \cdot \frac{\cosh\left(\frac{nz}{r}\right)}{\cosh(n \cdot s(1-m))}$ <p>where, $\tau_t = -\mu(\sigma_{res} - \nu_1 \cdot E_m \cdot \epsilon_1)$ and $n^2 = \frac{2 \cdot G_m}{E_f \cdot l \cdot v_f}$</p> <p>Average stress is calculated by integration over length of inclusion, z; other terms have usual meanings</p>	No change in average stress
C_{31}, C_{32}	$\sigma'_{incl} = \sigma_f$ if interface is perfect $\sigma'_{incl} = 0$ if interface is broken Average stress is calculated by volume weighted averaging; σ_f is the average stress in the inclusion that would be present if there is perfect interface in the inclusion	
C_{44}, C_{55}, C_{66}	$\sigma'_{incl} = \sigma_f$ if interface is perfect $\sigma'_{incl} = -\mu \sigma_{rr}$ if interface is broken and σ_n is negative $\sigma'_{incl} = 0$ if interface is broken and σ_n is positive Average stress is calculated by surface area weighted averaging of σ'_{incl} ; σ_{rr} is the stress component in the outward normal direction of the inclusion if there is perfect interface in the inclusion	

A number of FE-VE was created to validate the mechanical equivalence of the two composite systems, viz. the composite with imperfect interface, and the composite containing an *EqBI*. The mechanical equivalence here implies that both the effective response of composite systems and the average stresses in the inclusions must be similar for every possible type of loading.

We created a FE-VE with a single inclusion inside a matrix placed in such a way that the centroids of the matrix cuboid and the cylindrical inclusion coincide. The aspect ratio of the inclusion is taken to be 15 and the volume fraction is taken to be 0.1. This aspect ratio is chosen as it is a typical value of aspect ratio of inclusions in injection molded SFRC component. The cylindrical shape of the inclusion in the finite element VE is chosen to ensure acceptable mesh quality of the inclusion. Periodic boundary conditions are applied to the cubic cell. Both type A and B debonded interfaces are modelled by partitioning the inclusion and the matrix and using appropriate contact surface properties.

The contour stress plots calculated by the FE calculations are shown below in Figure 9 for axial loading cases for type A debonded interface. Also shown in the figure is the comparison of the average

stresses in the inclusion as well as the RVE. It is seen that the stresses in the inclusions as well as the composite are in good match with the FE results.

Figure 9 Comparison of average stresses in debonded inclusion and EqBI composite with debonded interface at the tip of inclusions (a) Stress contour in inclusions with debonded inclusion (b) average stress in inclusions (c) average stress in the RVE The contour stress plots calculated by the FE calculations are shown below in Figure 10 for axial loading cases for type B debonded interface. Also shown in the figure is the comparison of the average stresses in the inclusion as well as the RVE. A good match of the stresses in the inclusions as well as the composite is seen (with the FE results) also for Type B debonding.

Figure 10 Comparison of average stresses in debonded inclusion and EqBI composite with debonded interface at the equator of inclusions (a) Stress contour in inclusions with debonded inclusion (b) average stress in inclusions (c) average stress in the RVE.

For a detailed comparison of the stresses in the EqBI inclusion for a wide variety of loading cases and debonded interface configurations, the reader is advised to read [13].

Finally, for the experimental validations, Polybutylene terephthalate (PBT) reinforced with 50% weight fraction of glass fibre (equivalent volume fraction is 0.35) was injection molded to plates 170×170×2 mm. Coupons were machined from the plates in three directions, inclined at angles $\Phi = 0, 45$ and 90 with respect to the prevailing flow direction and subjected to tensile tests. They are referred to as 0, 45 and 90 degree coupon respectively. The stress strain curve for the matrix is taken to be the same as BASF Ultradur[®] B 4500. The coupons are subjected to tensile tests, the experimentally derived and the simulated stress strain curves are shown in Figure 9.

Figure 9: Simulation of stress strain behavior by matrix non-linearity only, fibre matrix debonding only and both together. (a) 0-degree coupon, (b) 45-degree coupon, (c) 90-degree coupon

Good match was observed for the three cases for the overall stress-strain behavior if both the fibre matrix debonding and matrix non-linearity is considered. It was also seen that for the 0 and 45 degree coupons, fibre matrix debonding is the major cause of non-linearity, while for the 90 degree coupons; the effect of the fibre matrix debonding is somewhat minimal. Matrix non-linearity is more important for the 90 degree coupons.

It was also seen that an approximate estimate of the tensile strength can be made by the proposed scheme. The predicted UTS for the 0, 45 and 90-degree coupons was 145, 71 and 51 MPa respectively, compared to the average experimental values of 126, 65 and 44 MPa respectively. The predicted strain to failure is always greater than the observed strain to failure. This is expected since in the MT formulation only the average stresses in the matrix are accounted for, but in reality final failure will most likely be due to stress concentrations in the matrix resulting out of several fibres accumulated in a region and subsequent crack propagations. These factors cannot be easily accounted

for within the framework of the MT formulation. If fibre matrix debonding is not considered, then the predicted strain to failure is somewhat lower. Fibre matrix debonding leads to reduction of stresses in the interface and consequently the average stress in the matrix, thus delaying the effect of contribution of matrix non-linearity to ultimate failure. A SFRC with very strong interface is expected to have a higher tensile stress, but a lower strain to failure.

5. CONCLUSIONS

Eshelby/Mori-Tanaka homogenisation with direct mean field homogenisation of an assembly of inclusions proved to provide adequate predictions for the mechanical behaviour of short and long wavy fibres reinforced composites for:

- homogenised elastic properties
- stress-strain state of individual inclusions
- interface stresses and debonding defined by these stresses
- stress-strain curves for tension loading of random fibre reinforced composites.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The work was funded by Baekeland CompFat project (IWT, Flanders) and by ModelSteelComp project in a Nanoforce program (SIM - Strategic Initiative Materials in Flanders and IWT - Flemish government agency for Innovation by Science and Technology), and supported by the Siemens Industry Software.

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